

NB-IoT: A Candidate Technology for mMTC in the 5G Era

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Abstract— The existing mobile network infrastructure is currently optimized to support the Narrow-Band Internet of Things (NB-IoT), which is meant to provide numerous services in poor coverage areas, with ultra-low power consumption. The question that arises is whether (and to what extent) NB-IoT can meet the requirement for massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) in the 5G era. In view of this, we study coverage enhancement in NB-IoT. We describe the subframe structure for various physical channels of NB-IoT and explain the repetition mechanism used for downlink transmissions in poor coverage areas. Focusing on optimizing this mechanism, we analyze how the latency and user blockage can be reduced by a proper selection of the downlink radio resources.

Keywords— NB-IoT, MAC Layer, mMTC, OFDM, PHY layer, Random access

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine Type Communication (MTC) is a communication paradigm where a number of devices or ‘things’ are attached to the Internet or directly connected and communicate with each other with little or without human intervention. In the 5G era, new applications for MTCs are developed to serve a huge number of ‘things’, introducing the so-called massive MTC (mMTC), or massive Internet of Things (mIoT) [1].

The challenge of massiveness has triggered the development of new wireless technologies for this communication paradigm. The main target is the development of systems that can support a huge number of low-cost devices that will consume ultra-low power and will support various types of services by being distributed in a wide area.

In this context, the Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWAN) have emerged [2]. As shown in Fig.1, there are different candidate technologies to support massive IoT over LPWAN. The LPWAN can be implemented over the unlicensed and licensed spectrum. The unlicensed LPWAN technologies, such as SigFox and LoRa (Long Range), are suitable for the budget conscious organization. The use of licensed spectrum over the existing cellular infrastructure guarantees a much more reliable and ubiquitous realization of the IoT concept. There are two potential candidate technologies for licensed spectrum

LPWAN: the enhanced machine type communication (eMTC) and the narrowband IoT (NB-IoT) [3]. The eMTC aims to support the broadest range of IoT applications which requires high data rate (up to 1 Mbps), full to limited mobility and voice/VoLTE facility, while NB-IoT serves IoT applications which are delay tolerant, requires very low data rate (in the order of kbps), and consumes ultra-low power. A detailed comparison of NB-IoT and eMTC is given in [3]. The eMTC and NB-IoT are two complementary technologies to support IoT application using the existing cellular network. We concentrate our study on NB-IoT because of its business benefits like improved power efficiency, cost savings, reliability, wider deployment and global reach, which attract many telecommunication service providers across the globe.

In this paper, a study on NB-IoT as a candidate technology for enabling massive IoT in the 5G era is presented. We consider the challenges of implementing the NB-IoT in the poor coverage area and analyze its performance with simulations. More precisely, the effect of subframe repetition is analyzed for different transport block size configurations. The obtained results show that NB-IoT can perform well in poor coverage areas, with acceptable block error rate, by properly managing the available resources.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. The key requirements and challenges for massive IoT are described in section II, and the NB-IoT technology is reviewed in section III. The design choice of downlink radio resource in NB-IoT and related evaluation results are presented in section IV and V respectively.

Figure 1: Candidate technologies for massive IoT

II. ENABLING MTC IN THE 5G ERA

The development of 5G networks is progressing at a rapid pace, and 5G systems are expected in the market by 2020 [4]. 5G systems have the ambition of bringing together a wide range of services and applications under the same umbrella. These applications and services lie in a well-known triangle, whose vertices are defined by the following three service extremes:

1. Extreme mobile broadband (eMBB)
2. Massive machine type communication (mMTC) or Massive IoT
3. Low latency and ultra-reliable communication (URLLC)

mMTC, as one of the service extremes in this triangle has attracted a lot of interest from research and innovation bodies. Forecasts state that the number of connected devices in the 5G era will be 10 times more than it is today [1]. This sheer number of devices imposes additional requirements on the network for effectively supporting massive device connections without degrading the existing human type communication (HTC). The requirements and challenges of implementing mMTC over the 5G network are described next [5], [6].

A. System requirements

Massive device volume: In 5G, the number of autonomously communicating devices within a cell will be of the order of tens of thousands. This scenario will lead to massive concurrent access attempts to a limited spectrum.

Small sized data transmission: In most of the MTC applications, data are transmitted in a small packet, periodically in the uplink direction.

Uplink dominance: In mMTC, the dominant communication direction is uplink, while the downlink channel is mostly used for the exchange of control information.

Low to high mobility: Mobility requirements in mMTC will vary significantly with the application. For applications, such as smart metering and environment sensing, mobility is almost zero. On the other hand, in MTC applications involving vehicular communications, mobility is high.

Time controlled: Like the mobility requirements, delay tolerance in MTC also varies significantly with the application. For instance, applications such as smart metering have very relaxed delay requirements; on the other hand, many applications in e-health care have very tight delay constraints.

Group-based policing: In MTC applications, devices with similar requirements or in the same geographic area are grouped together to provide better radio resource management, e.g., better energy efficiency and congestion control.

Periodic and burst traffic: The MTC system should be able to support both periodic and burst traffic scenarios. For example, in an application such as environmental sensing in a control plant, if anything unusual is noticed, the generated event should be conveyed as quickly as possible.

B. Technical Challenges in PHY and MAC

The system design requirements of MTC impose new challenges on PHY and MAC. Below we list the main challenges on the PHY and MAC layers that need to be addressed to effectively support MTC [7] [8].

Massive access: In 5G MTC, large numbers of machines will need to simultaneously access the limited available spectrum. This massive access will cause collisions in the random access (RA) channel, causing packet losses and delays. It might also cause an unacceptable performance degradation to HTC. So, appropriate control mechanisms should be designed and implemented at the MAC layer for the efficient sharing of the limited available resources.

Control overhead: In MTC, data are transmitted in small packets. So, we cannot afford large signaling overhead to support MTC, as it will reduce the efficiency of data transmission. So, the MAC protocols must be appropriately modified to minimize the transmission control overhead for MTC applications.

Adaptability: In MTC, the network traffic and the number of connected devices might be highly variable, as devices enter and leave the network dynamically. So, the MAC protocol should be able to adapt to dynamic network conditions.

Security: For MTC, security must be provided for both communication and data. This is because most of the time MTC sensors are deployed in an unprotected environment. Hence somebody can move the sensors or misuse them. The challenge is to provide this level of security with power limited low-cost MTC sensors.

Reliability and low latency: Ultra reliable communication is vital for mission-critical MTC applications such as e-health care, safety, and control mechanisms in a gas-plant, autonomous driving cars, etc. The current LTE system does not support this functionality. Here the challenge is to support diverse QoS for mMTC applications.

Energy efficiency: Most of the M2M devices are battery operated and expected to work without replacement for a long time period. So, the MAC layer should avoid the energy consumption due to the exchange of excessive control information. Also, multi-access packet collisions should be controlled to reduce energy consuming packet retransmissions.

Cost-effectiveness: Because of the large-scale deployment, MAC protocols based on highly complex hardware modules should be avoided in M2M communications.

Co-existence: Due to the cost of spectrum usage in a licensed band, a significant portion of M2M communications will operate in unlicensed spectrum. With the widespread deployment of M2M devices in the unlicensed band, it is likely that multiple M2M access networks will be deployed independently nearby each other and in the same unlicensed band. This will cause interference that needs to be managed.

Enhanced coverage area: Coverage is an important parameter for wide area sensor networks, where sensors are deployed in challenging areas. To ensure proper communication between the M2M device domain and the M2M communication domain, coverage enhancement is vital.

III. THE NB-IOT TECHNOLOGY

This section describes the physical layer structure of NB-IoT. Different modes of operation and physical channels of NB-IoT are explained here.

A. NB-IoT Physical Layer

The NB-IoT is configured to support a bandwidth of 180 kHz, which is equal to one physical resource block (PRB) and thus can be served together with the other LTE UEs by the same eNB. This allows NB-IoT deployment with the existing infrastructure just by applying a software update. NB-IoT supports a peak data rate of 234.7 kbps in the downlink and 204.8 kbps in the uplink, and half duplex frequency division multiplexing [9].

NB-IoT is designed to work in three operational modes: 1) In-band, 2) guard-band, and 3) stand-alone, as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: NB-IoT operational modes

B. Slot and Frame Structure

In the downlink, the frame and slot structure of NB-IoT is the same as that of LTE. OFDM modulation is applied using 15 KHz subcarrier spacing with a normal cyclic prefix. A subframe has a duration of 1 ms. Subframes are summed up into radio frames in the same way as in LTE [10].

In the uplink, both single-tone and multi-tone transmissions are supported. The multi-tone transmissions are based on SC-FDMA with 15 kHz subcarrier spacing. In this case, the slot and frame

structure is the same as that of the downlink. For single-tone transmission, two numerologies are configured by the network: 3.75 kHz and 15 kHz. The 15 kHz subcarrier spacing is the same as that for LTE. For uplink transmission at 3.75 KHz, a radio frame of length 10 ms is considered, consisting of 5 subframes of length 2 ms. This 2 ms, subframe allocation has the same transmission efficiency as that of legacy LTE [10] [12].

C. Narrow-band Uplink Channel

For NB-uplink there are two physical channels: 1) Narrowband physical random access channel (NPRACH), and 2) Narrowband physical uplink shared channel (NPUSCH).

NPRACH

In NB-IoT, random access is always contention based and starts with a preamble transmission on single-tone NPRACH. NPRACH is a newly designed physical uplink channel having a bandwidth of 180 KHz. The NPRACH preamble is based on a symbol group, on a single carrier. A subcarrier spacing of 3.75 KHz is applied. Each symbol group comprises one cyclic prefix and 5 symbols, and the NPRACH preamble consists of such 4-preamble groups as shown in Fig. 3 [11]. Each symbol group is transmitted on different subcarriers (frequency hopping) to facilitate accurate timing estimation. Based on which coverage level the UE is operating, the preamble group is repeated to improve the probability of successful reception at eNodeB.

NPUSCH

NB-IoT NPUSCH has two formats. Format 1 is used for carrying the data, and format 2 is used for signaling HARQ acknowledgments for NPDSCH (NB-IoT physical downlink shared channel). Format 1 uses turbo codes for error correction and format 2 uses repetition-based error correction. The NPUSCH format 1 supports both single-tone and multi-tone operation. The single tone operation is either based on 3.75 KHz or 15 KHz numerology [9] [12].

Figure 3: An illustration of NPRACH frequency hopping

D. Narrow-band downlink channel

For NB-downlink, three physical channel is defined and all the downlink channels in NB-IoT use QPSK modulated. In the sequel, NB-downlink physical channels are explained in more detail.

Narrowband physical broadcast channel (NPBCH)

NPBCH carries the master system information block (MIB), which contains the essential system information such as system frame number for initial cell access. The MIB-NB contains 34-bit information transmitted over 64 radio frames. Within this 64 radio frames, there are 8 blocks of NPBCH, each having a unique scrambling code. To support in-band deployment and to avoid collisions with LTE multicast/broadcast, each NPBCH block is transmitted in the first subframe of each radio frame and is repeated 8 times, as shown in the Fig. 4.

Figure 4: NB-IoT physical broadcast channel (NPBCH) structure

Narrowband physical downlink control channel (NPDCCH)

NPDCCH carries the information regarding resource assignment for NPDSCH or scheduling grant for NPUSCH. The downlink control information (DCI) in the NPDCCH indicates where the above-mentioned information can be found, how often it is repeated. Also, NPDCCH carries additional information such as paging or system information updates.

NPDCCH and NPDSCH are multiplexed using TDM at the subframe level at least per UE, which means that only cross-subframe scheduling is supported. Downlink (DL) transmissions to UEs in extreme coverage conditions may require many repetitions and thereby block the DL for other UEs. Intermediate transmission gaps at well-defined time instants during long DL transmissions are introduced to avoid this blocking.

Narrowband physical downlink shared channel (NPDSCH)

NPDSCH is the traffic channel and it has a maximum transport block 680 bits. The number of subframes (NS) and the number of repetitions (R) of the NPDSCH are mentioned in the DCI. The resulting NPDSCH sequence is mapped over a total of $N \times R$ consecutive

subframes. The NPDSCH subframe has the structure shown in Fig. 5. For in-band operation, NB-IoT operation needs to protect the LTE control channels and signals that coexist within the NB-IoT resources that NPDSCH is mapped to (first 3 OFDM symbols in the subframe). For this purpose, the start of NPDSCH is indicated by a parameter I_{start} , so that the entire legacy control region is protected. The control region is protected in other DL channels too (NPBCH and NPDCCH) using the same procedure.

Repetition of NPDSCH subframes should be supported for UEs in enhanced coverage. A maximum of 2048 repetition is allowed for NPDSCH. Similar to NPDCCH, to prevent the downlink PRB from being blocked during a long NPDSCH transmission for a UE in extreme coverage areas, discontinuous transmission is supported in NPDSCH.

Figure 5: NPDSCH subframe structure (in-band operation)

IV. THE PROBLEM UNDER STUDY

The NB-IoT supports three coverage classes defined in terms of maximum coupling losses (MCL) as follows: 1) Normal coverage – MCL 144 dB, 2) Robust coverage – MCL 154 dB, and 3) Extreme coverage – MCL 164 dB. Based on which coverage class a UE selects, the physical channels of NB-IoT is repeated accordingly to maintain an acceptable block error rate (BLER). The BLER is defined as the ratio of the number of erroneous blocks to the total number of transmitted blocks. From [15], it is desired to have a BLER of less than 10% for NPDSCH. The repetition of the physical channels introduces additional latency and blocks the resources available for other users in the cell. In this section, we analyze how available resources can be managed properly to reduce delay and user blockage.

The scheduler in the eNodeB controls the allocation of shared resources among users at each time. In our study, we choose resource scheduling in the NPDSCH. This is because, in this study, we focus on comparative analysis of delay and user blockage based on the choice of NS and R, without considering the possible collisions in the uplink. From 3GPP TS 36.213 Table 16.4.1.5.1-1, transport block size (TBS) table, we can observe that an NPDSCH transport block size can be

generated by different methods. For example, a TBS of 680 bits can be generated by using 10 subframes and applying MCS of 4, and by using 3 subframes and MCS of 12. This is true for other TBS too. The total number of subframes occupied by an NPDSCH is given by the product of the number of subframes (NS) for NPDSCH and the number of repetitions (R) for NPDSCH. We performed a link level simulation to analyze the choice of this NS and R on BLER, latency and user blockage.

In the simulation, a data of desired transport block size as defined in [14] undergoes CRC encoding, convolutional encoding, and rate matching to obtain the NPDSCH bits, which are repeated according to a specific subframe repetition pattern. Modulation is applied to generate the complex NPDSCH symbols and then transmitted over the channel where additive white Gaussian noise is added to the complex symbols. At the receiver end, the process done in the transmitter is repeated in reverse order to recover the transport block.

V. EVALUATION RESULT

For the evaluation study, we used Matlab NB-IoT toolbox. First, we assumed a UE that selects the extended coverage (i.e., robust coverage class (SNR = -4.8 dB) and extreme coverage class (SNR = -9.8 dB) [15]). Fig. 6 presents the obtained BLER for 680 bits TBS for a different number of subframe repetition and Fig. 7 presents the obtained BLER for 680-bit TBS for NS = 10, MCS = 4 and NS = 3, MCS = 12 in the extended coverage area for different numbers of subframe repetitions.

Figure 6: NPDSCH block error rate variation with the number of subframe repetition.

From Fig. 6, we can observe that, as the number of repetitions increases, BLER decreases. This is because all the subframes in a bundle are used to decode the transport block at the UE. As with the increase in subframe repetition, the UE has more signal power accumulated, which improves the BLER. In an AWGN affected channel, with 16 or more subframe repetitions, the BLER can be maintained below 10% in the extended coverage area.

It can be observed from Fig. 7 that both TBS choices, i.e., NS = 10, MCS = 4 and NS = 3, MCS = 12, give a similar BLER. But if we use NS = 10, the NPDSCH codeword is spread over 10 subframes, and each subframe is repeated R times. In this case, the UE uses more resources compared to NS = 3, MCS = 4. This eventually blocks the other UEs in the cell. In addition, the UE must wait for all the subframes to start the decoding the NPDSCH. According to [13], NB-IoT must support a minimum of 55K users in a cell, hence blocking of the resources and a larger number of NPDSCH subframes increases the latency to support a massive number of devices. Thus, to reduce resource blocking and latency, a lower number of NPDSCH subframes should be used.

Figure 7: NPDSCH block error rate simulation for the UE's operating in the extended coverage class, having a TBS of 680 bits.

To analyze the effect of the choice of downlink scheduling parameters, i.e. NS and MCS on latency and user blockage, we simulate a multi-user NB-IoT system. It is assumed that a number of users are already scheduled and waiting for their downlink data in NPDSCH. Based on the work carried out in [16], we consider a maximum of 300 simultaneous users, which are successfully completed the RA procedure and scheduled for downlink data. The users are evenly distributed in each coverage level. It can be observed from Fig. 8 that as the number of subframe spreading increases, the time taken serve all the scheduled users increases. This is because the user has to wait for all the $NS \times R$ subframes to arrive to decode the NPDSCH data. The NB-IoT has a delay requirement (D_{max}) of 10 seconds [17] [18]. Fig. 9 shows the number of users which received the downlink data (mentioned as 'served users' now onwards) within this D_{max} time bound. Similar to latency result, as the number of NPDSCH subframe spreading increases, total number of served users within D_{max} decreases. From the simulation conducted with 300 simultaneous scheduled users, having a TBS of 680 bits (maximum possible TBS in downlink), maximum of 258 users only served within the time-bound D_{max} . This is the best-case scenario, meaning, in this study we did not

consider the processing time required for cell synchronization, RA process, and uplink allocation [16]. We assumed that entire D_{\max} is available for downlink data transmission. So, in practice, the time available for downlink data transmission is less than D_{\max} .

Figure 8: Time consumed to serve all the users scheduled for NPDSCH, having a TBS of 680 bits.

Figure 9: Number of served downlink scheduled users within D_{\max} time bound.

VI. CONCLUSION

Extending the coverage of existing cellular system is vital to support massive internet of things. The NB-IoT enhances the coverage by repetition of subframes. The extensive repetition of a subframe in the extreme coverage area blocks the transmission from other UEs in the cell, and thus, increases the latency. This paper considers the choice of subframe spreading and modulation and coding scheme configuration for downlink scheduled users to minimize latency and number of blocked users. We found that the blockage and latency can be reduced by choosing the fewer number of subframes for a desired transport block size. In our future work, we will jointly optimize all the parameters in the DCI (subframe spreading, MCS, scheduling delay and the number of repetition) to minimize the latency and user blockage.

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REFERENCES

- [1] 5GPPP Vision: The 5G Infrastructure Public-Private Partnership: the next generation of communication networks and services.
- [2] L. Krupka, L. Vojtech, and M. Neruda, "The issue of LPWAN technology coexistence in IoT environment," 2016 17th International Conference on Mechatronics - Mechatronika (ME), Prague, 2016, pp. 1-8.
- [3] A. Chakrapani, "Efficient resource scheduling for eMTC/NB-IoT communications in LTE Rel. 13," 2017 IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (CSCN), Helsinki, 2017, pp. 66-71.
- [4] W. Ejaz et al., "Internet of Things (IoT) in 5G Wireless Communications," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 4, pp. 10310-10314, 2016.
- [5] H. Shariatmadari et al., "Machine-type communications: current status and future perspectives toward 5G systems," in *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 53, no. 9, pp. 10-17, September 2015.
- [6] N. Xia, H. H. Chen and C. S. Yang, "Radio Resource Management in Machine-to-Machine Communications—A Survey," in *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 791-828, First quarter 2018.
- [7] C. Bockelmann et al., "Massive machine-type communications in 5g: physical and MAC-layer solutions," in *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 54, no. 9, pp. 59-65, September 2016.
- [8] A. Rajandekar and B. Sikdar, "A Survey of MAC Layer Issues and Protocols for Machine-to-Machine Communications," in *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 175-186, April 2015.
- [9] Y. P. E. Wang et al., "A Primer on 3GPP Narrowband Internet of Things," in *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 117-123, March 2017.
- [10] R1-160183 "Uplink frame structure design" NB-PUSCH design, Huawei, HiSilicon, China Telecom, 3GPP TSG RAN WG1 NB-IoT Ad-Hoc Meeting, Budapest, January 2016.
- [11] R1-160025, "NB-PRACH design", Huawei, HiSilicon, Neul, RAN1 NB-IoT ad-hoc meeting, Budapest, January 2016.
- [12] "Narrow-Band Internet of Things White paper – Rohde & Schwarz"
- [13] R1-160315, "NB-PDCCH resource mapping", Huawei, HiSilicon, 3GPP TSG RAN WG1 Meeting #84, Malta, February 2016.
- [14] 3GPP TS 36.213 V14.2.0. "Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access (E-UTRA); Physical layer procedures," Apr. 2017
- [15] 3GPP TS 36.104 V14.3.0. "Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access (E-UTRA); Base Station (BS) Radio Transmission and Reception," Apr. 2017
- [16] R. Harwahu, R. G. Cheng, C. H. Wei and R. F. Sari, "Optimization of Random Access Channel in NB-IoT," in *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 391-402, Feb. 2018.
- [17] R. Ratasuk, B. Vejlgaard, N. Mangalvedhe and A. Ghosh, "NB-IoT system for M2M communication," 2016 *IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference Workshops (WCNCW)*, Doha, 2016, pp. 428-432.
- [18] R. Boisguene, S. C. Tseng, C. W. Huang and P. Lin, "A survey on NB-IoT downlink scheduling: Issues and potential solutions," 2017 *13th International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing Conference (IWCMC)*, Valencia, 2017, pp. 547-551.